

SPECIFIC FEATURES AND THE PROBLEMS OF ALLITERATION
IN MODERN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Pazilova Nasibaxon Muhammadqosimovna¹

¹Docent, Andijan State foreign languages Institute
npazilova304@gmail.com

G'ofurova Gullola Axmadullayevna²

²First-Year Student of Master's degree Andijan State foreign
languages Institute
gofurovagullola@gmail.com

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Annotation. This article analyses the importance of alliteration in literature which discusses specific features of alliteration in Modern English and Uzbek.

Key words: repetition, alliteration, utterance, distinction, stressed syllable, artistic style, poetic features.

In linguistics, alliteration is most often considered as "symmetrical repetition of homogeneous consonants" in the speech flow, which is opposed to assonance - "symmetrical repetition of homogeneous vowels" [6, p. 27]. An alliteration makes on the repetition of a consonant or groups of consonants at the beginning of words of one utterance is not distinguished into an independent group.

As far as the English language tradition is concerned, Webster's definition of the word "Alliteration" is characteristic: "The repetition usu. initially of a sound that is usu. a consonant in two or more neighboring words or syllables (as wild and wooly, threatening throng)" [14]. The definition of this term in the Oxford English Dictionary is also significant: "The commencing of two or more words in close connection, with the same letter, or rather the same sound" [13]. This alliteration in the English-language linguistic tradition is distinguished by:

- 1) predominantly the initial position of the repeated sound in the word;
- 2) not as rigid as in Russian linguistics, the distinction between alliteration and assonance.

Alliteration in English is deeply rooted in the traditions of folk art. The literary form of ancient English poetry differed from the modern literary forms of poetic works. In this poetry, rhythm and alliteration were the main points of the verse. Each significant word in the line of folk songs, legends, which was under stress, began with the same combination of sounds.

Alliteration in ancient Saxon poetry played the same role that rhyme plays in modern poetry. Alliteration can be called the initial rhyme: it is not the last syllable of the word that rhymes, but the initial sounds of the word.

In modern English, alliteration is understood not only as the repetition of initial sounds, but also sounds in the middle of a word. Folk tradition, as you know, is always vitally stable and the reception of alliteration, as an artistic form of folk poetic works, has remained in the English language as a proven means of artistic and emotional impact on the reader. Unlike the Russian language, where alliteration did not have such deep roots in folk art, in English alliteration is widely used as an artistic and stylistic device not only in poetry, but also in artistic prose.

Alliteration can be seen in the headlines of newspapers and in the titles of literary works, for example:

Sense and Sensibility;

Pride and Prejudice;

School for Scandal;

A Book of Phable and Phrase.

Alliteration is of particular importance to the English language, since Anglo-Saxon verse was alliterative. She performed the function of a kind of metronome of the work - unstressed syllables were pronounced at approximately the same time intervals: quickly, if there were a lot of them, and slowly, if there were few of them. Under such conditions, the beginning of the stressed syllable was the most important section of the word, and alliteration emphasized precisely these functionally significant points of the verse. Alliteration in Russian does not have such deep roots.[1]

Let us turn to English literature to give examples of the use of alliteration. The Anglo-Saxon epic poem "Beowulf" is one of the most striking examples of works in which the use of alliteration is often found.

Translated into modern English, "Beowulf" (Modern English) is as follows:

Stone-bright the street: it showed the way
to the crowd of clansmen. Corselets glistened
hand-forged, hard; on their harness bright
the steel ring sang, as they strode along
in mail of battle, and marched to the hall.

The exact reproduction of the poetic features of the original in Russian would be contrary to the norms of modern poetics. Here is an excerpt from the translation of the poem "Beofulf" translated into Russian:

On colorful slabs
on the paved path
the crowd stepped

armored men
in military outfits
in chain mail, ringing
iron rings,
strong links,
army brilliant
went to the yard.

The translator of Beowulf retained the alliteration (although not always on the first syllable), but he could not retain its ancient function, so the reader in most cases will not even hear these consonances.

Consider Edgar Allan Poe's The Raven as another example of the use of alliteration in English. It is known that the main theme in Edgar Poe's poem "The Raven" is the theme of love and death, in which love emphasizes the horror of death, and death emphasizes the strength and invincibility of love. Here, gloomy depression echoes hopeless grief.

As of someone gently rapping, rapping at my chamber door - "Tis some visiter," I muttered, "tapping at my chamber door -

Eagerly I wished the morrow; - vainly I had sought to borrow
From my books surcease of sorrow - sorrow for the lost Lenore

Deep into that darkness peering, long I stood there wondering, fearing,
Doubting, dreaming dreams no mortal ever dared to dream before;

Thrilled me - filled me with fantastic terrors never felt before; So that now, to
still the beating of my heart, I stood repeating

But the silence was unbroken, and the stillness gave no token, And the only word
there spoken was the whispered word, "Lenore!"

In fact, this passage describes the same feeling, but we read between the lines we see the sick love of the hero, and we also see this from the biography of E. Poe, who, after the loss of his wife, he could not find a place for himself, was in despair and could not imagine his life without a loved one. The sound [r] is associated with the growl of a dog. The combination of sounds [t] and [p] resembles raindrops. The sound [d] is most often associated with the drum.

Words in which the combination of letters gives "ill" is associated with the translation of this word (illness, illness, pain associated with experiences).

The combination of letters and sounds, reminiscent of the word "anger", is also associated with anger, hatred and unpleasant emotions.

Thus, it can be assumed that it is alliteration that plays a very important role in this work, and associations are used to build a general idea of what the author wanted to convey, what his intention was.

We can say that the use of alliteration in the poem "The Raven" is deliberate, carries a secret plan and a set of negative emotions that the author wanted to convey. Aesthetics, poetic principles, artistic style of E. Poe are so peculiar that he, using romantic themes, traditional romantic ideas, images, largely departed from them and even parodied them.

The next work, recognized as one of the most interesting and memorable works that use the technique of alliteration, is the "Song of Hiawatha" by Henry Wadsworth Longfellow.

Here alliteration acts as a means of strengthening stressed syllables. Alliteration, as a way of strengthening stressed syllables, is often limited to one verse and is a repetition of a sound in two words (alliteration in paired words).

But he gravely spake and answered

To their jeering and their jesting: (XXI, 183-184)

But these guests I leave behind me,

In your watch and ward I leave them; (XXII, 182-185)

Here, the initial sound is repeated in pairs of homogeneous members of sentences connected by the union and. The sequence stressed syllable + unstressed and + stressed syllable is reinforced by the alliteration of the initial sound.

At the junction of words, alliteration of a whole group of sounds can occur.

Boastful breath is not a bow string (IX, 179)

The first syllable begins with the sounds [boust]. They are repeated at the end of the line as a result of the collision of the stressed word bow and the unstressed string. Here is another case of alliteration of three sounds at the beginning of two different words.

Alliteration of sound as a way of increasing stress can be observed in segments longer than one line and spanning up to three or four lines.

Alliteration very often serves to highlight the key word of an utterance or superphrasal unity. It usually draws two or more lines. Alliteration as a way to highlight a keyword is a repetition of the initial sound or sound combination of a keyword in other words of a verse or several verses.

Taller than the tallest tree-tops! (XXI, 161)

From his pouch he drew his peace-pipe, (XXI, 21)

Shot the wild goose, flying southward
On the wing, the clamorous Wawa; (X, 93-94)
Hear the story of Osseo,
Son of the Evening Star, Osseo! (XII, 28-29)
He the idle Yenadizze,
He the merry mischief-maker, (XI, 56-67)
Full of new and strange adventures,
Marvels many and many wonders. (XXI, 141-142)

Despite the special role of alliteration and assonance in translation and conveying the meaning, expressions can be omitted due to the difficult selection of an equivalent in the language into which the translation is carried out. The linguistic phenomena we are considering in the translation and transmission of the meaning of the expression can be omitted, and appear both in English and in Russian as secondary and cannot be called "necessary".

Speaking of alliteration in English prose, translators most often mean anaphoric alliteration and anaphoric assonance. These types of sound repetitions are indeed not so characteristic of Russian prose - although they are not completely alien to it. Let's cite just a few cases.

"Rocket! It crumbled into a rose, a swarm of multi-colored moles, giving birth to a joyful roar of mouths. Wheels were spinning, swings, skates, sail skirts, stockings, stripes of the body above them. Someone is pumping the camel's muzzle high like a pump. Everyone shied away at once, as if Clement XII himself was driving the flock from place to place with a pastoral broom." (M. Kuzmin, "The Wonderful Life of Joseph Balsamo, Count of Cagliostro")

In this regard, some theories are interesting that try to prove that individual sounds or combinations of sounds have additional shades of meaning or a special expressive power. So, some literary critics argue that "different sounds and their various combinations have different expressive power." Others go further. They endow separate sounds with the ability to express ideas and feelings and argue that in the work of a true poet there is a relationship between the sounds of words, thoughts and feelings that they express.

One of the largest experts in English versification, the French scientist Verrier, recommends pronouncing some vowel sound (A, I, U) with your eyes closed, articulating it strongly and distinctly. So he comes to the conclusion that the sound (U) usually expresses sadness, seriousness; the sound (I) inspires joy, and so on.

Interesting data are provided by L.I. Timofeev in his work "Theory of Literature": "P.A. Vyazemsky refuted this theory that sounds have a certain meaning in a dispute with an Italian who did not know Russian, with a proposal to determine the meaning of words by sound - love, friendship, friend. The Italian suggested that it was "something tough, harsh, maybe abusive." And when asked what the word veal could mean by its sounds, he replied that there was no doubt that this word was affectionate, gentle, addressed to a woman.

In English fiction and especially in poetry, alliteration is considered as a powerful means of expressing the feelings and emotions of the poet. Speech sounds are seen as having their own emotional meaning. So, for example, the sound [d] is considered as a sound that produces a gloomy, sinister effect, [l], on the contrary, is an expression of tenderness and warm feelings. Of course, it cannot be denied that certain sounds enhance the effect that is achieved by the meaning of the utterance. So the repetition of the sound [d] in the following lines below is designed to enhance the suppressed, mystical mood created by the entire poem by E. Poe "The Raven":

Deep into that darkness peering, long I stood there wondering, fearing,
Doubting, dreaming dreams no mortal ever dared to dream before." [12]

Theories about the semantic independence of sounds are based on the subjective interpretation of sound associations. It is quite obvious that sounds in themselves, as well as specially organized repetition sounds, cannot be carriers of any ideological, semantic content.

These repetition sounds, of course, are a kind of means of artistic expression, they can also perform a certain artistic function, for example, enhance the emotional impact on the reader, create a certain tone of the utterance, and sometimes, as will be shown below, and cause a certain association with objectively existing natural sounds in nature, but from this they do not become carriers of a certain meaning.

The question of whether a single sound can express an idea and feelings is debatable, but it is absolutely certain that such a stylistic device as alliteration has an impact on the audience. This can be proved by how wide the scope of the use of alliteration is now. Why is alliteration so popular? The fact is that phrases that consist of words starting with the same letter are very easy to remember, pronounce and perceive by ear.

For example:

Stores: Sushi Station, Coffee Corner, Dunkin' Donuts.

Products and brands: Coca-cola, FireFox, BlackBerry, PayPal.

Movies: V for Vendetta.

Characters: Donald Duck, Mickey Mouse, Peter Pan, Prince of Persia.

Newspaper Headlines: Fighting Football Fans Face Fines

Advertising slogans: Don't dream it. Drive it (Jaguar slogan).

My Goodness, My Guinness! (Guinness slogan).

Aliases: Marilyn Monroe, Marilyn Manson

In English, there are a number of simple words built on the principle of alliteration.

Brickbat

For all the brickbats it has received, it's a good plan.

Mishmash

Her collection is a mishmash of different styles.

Pitter-patter

She heard the pitter-patter of rain on the window panes.

Rat race

He is quitting the rat race to spend time with her family.

Shipshape

Everything had to be shipshape before we could sell the house.

Sob story

I don't want to hear any of your sob stories.

Wishy-washy

A report which is wishy-washy makes a bad impression.

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